
A Systematic Review on the Effects of Yoga on Gait Performance for Older Adults

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Abstract Gait defined as the pattern of movement of the limbs during locomotion as a fundamental aspect of mobility in humans. It is one of the keys to movement around the environment and from one place to another. Physiological changes in the neuromuscular, musculoskeletal and sensory systems, all of which contribute to alterations in gait patterns. Yoga, a multi-component mind-body practice, improves several domains of physical and psychological health that help to improve in gait parameters. The purpose of this systematic review is to study the effectiveness of yoga-based interventions in improving gait among older adults. This systematic review includes only randomized controlled trials reviewed from electronic databases: PubMed, Science Direct, Cochrane, Scopus and Web of Science and search engine Google Scholar. RCTs include yoga as a therapeutic intervention for gait in older adults aged above 60 years only. This systematic review demonstrates that yoga interventions have shown significant benefits in improving gait parameters among older adults.

Keywords: gait, yoga, older adults, elders

Introduction

Gait is achieved by coordinated movements of body segments, taking advantage of an interaction between internal and external factors. It is accomplished through the action of the neuromusculoskeletal system. Normal gait is both stable and flexible allowing for changes in speed and maneuvering in different terrains while maintaining energetic efficiency (Mirelman *et al.*, 2018). The speed at which a person walks influences biomechanical variables such as joint kinematics, ground reaction forces (GRF), joint moments of force (moments) and powers, muscle activity, and spatiotemporal gait parameters in children, young adults, and older adults (Fukuchi *et al.*, 2019). Gait is a complex motor activity involving the coordination of the musculoskeletal and nervous system essential for independent mobility in daily life. In older adult gait undergoes significant changes due to age-related physiological declines in muscle strength, proprioception, vestibular function and central nervous system processing (Abellan van Kan *et al.*, 2009). These changes often manifest as slower gait speed, shorter stride length, increased variability and reduced balance control collectively referred to as age-related gait impairment. Alterations in gait are not merely biomechanical issues; they are also strong predictors of adverse health outcomes in the elderly. Gait speed often termed the “sixth vital sign” is a well-established biomarker of overall health and functional status (Studenski *et al.*, 2011). Slower gait speed has been associated with increased risk of falls, disability, hospitalization, cognitive decline and mortality (Montero-Odasso *et al.*, 2005; Verghese *et al.*, 2007). Gait disorders in older adults often coexist with cognitive impairments particularly in executive function highlighting the importance of evaluating gait under dual-task conditions (Hausdorff *et al.*, 2005). A large-scale

survey of 9,174 Indian adults aged ≥ 60 years found that 22.9% reported partial or complete walking disability highlighting that nearly one in five older Indians experience substantial mobility challenges (Srivastava *et al.*, 2022). Yoga is an ancient mind-body discipline that originated in India over 5,000 years ago and encompasses a comprehensive system of practices aimed at promoting physical, mental and spiritual well-being. The word “yoga” is derived from the Sanskrit root “yuj” meaning “to unite” or “to join” referring to the integration of body, mind and spirit (Woodyard, 2011). In contemporary health sciences yoga is increasingly recognized as a complementary therapy with measurable benefits across a variety of physical and psychological health domains. The practice typically involves a combination of asanas (physical postures), pranayama (breathing techniques) and dhyana (meditation) which together contribute to improving flexibility, balance, cardiovascular health, neuromuscular function and psychological resilience (Field, 2011; Büssing *et al.*, 2012). Scientific investigations have demonstrated that regular yoga practice can lead to reductions in stress, anxiety and inflammation, while also enhancing musculoskeletal function, autonomic regulation and immune activity (Pascoe & Bauer, 2015; Cramer *et al.*, 2016). Low-impact and adaptable nature yoga has been successfully implemented among diverse populations including older adults individuals with musculoskeletal disorders, cardiovascular diseases and mental health conditions (Birdee *et al.*, 2009).

Material and Methods

Search Strategies:

The studies included in this systematic review were identified through comprehensive electronic searches of the databases PubMed, ScienceDirect, Cochrane, Scopus, Web of Science and Google Scholar. The review focused on English-language scientific publications specially randomized controlled trials published between 2015 and 2025. The primary method for locating relevant literature was systematic online database searching. The search strategy incorporated the keywords “Gait” AND “Yoga” to retrieve studies aligned with the research objective.

Screening and selection: The selection process followed a sequential screening approach beginning with the titles and abstracts followed by in-depth evaluation of the full-text articles and study design. Each study was assessed systematically to determine its eligibility based on the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria: This systematic review included randomized controlled trials (RCTs) published in English that were open access and provided full-text availability. Eligible studies focused on the categories of “gait” and “yoga” and involved participants aged 60 years or older experiencing gait-related health issues.

Exclusion Criteria: The present systematic review excluded thesis, books, review articles, case studies, surveys, study protocols, pilot studies and meta-analyses. In addition studies were excluded if they were not published in English did not involve yoga or gait as a focus or included participants under the age of 60.

Data Extraction: A comprehensive evaluation was carried out for all studies that met the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Key information extracted from each study included the author(s), year of publication, study design, sample size, age group, intervention time and intervention type and relevant statistical outcomes. Any uncertainties or discrepancies encountered during the data extraction process were resolved through mutual discussion and collaboration.

Results

This review ultimately included a total of seven studies [Figure 1]. The initial database search identified 191 articles. 18 from PubMed, 63 from ScienceDirect, 36 from the Cochrane, 34 from Scopus, 25 Web of Science and 15 from Google Scholar. After removing 38 duplicates, 191 articles were screened based on titles and abstracts and 7 full text articles were considered for inclusion.

Following the application of the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 146 articles were excluded. Thirty two studies were not relevant to the study. Fourteen review and meta-analysis were excluded from the study. Two for no full article and seven for study protocol were excluded. Twenty eight for studies were under age. Thirty three were related to gait but not with yoga. Eleven pilot studies were excluded, as were sixteen studies that did not follow a randomized controlled trial design. One case study, one non-English publication and one thesis were also excluded from the final analysis.

Figure 1: Flow Chart of Systematic Literature Review

Discussion

Of the 191 papers screened 7 randomized controlled trial were examined and included for discussion [Table 1] demonstrates a significant impact on gait. The studies included in this review highlight the growing interest in yoga as a therapeutic intervention for improving gait among older adults. Across the seven studies examined there is a consistent trend indicating that yoga whether practiced alone or in combination with other interventions such as dietary modification or conventional physiotherapy has a positive effect on gait and mobility-related outcomes. A randomized controlled trial involved 46 participants with non-specific chronic low back pain (mean age, 68.7 \pm 5.1 years), randomly allocated to either an experimental group or a control group. The experimental group participated in a 4-night, 5-day intervention comprising heated peat pack therapy, mindfulness meditation, core exercises, and local tourism. Marine healing program in which mindfulness meditation was given improved gait in participants (Baek *et al.*, 2025). Another randomized controlled trial by Carcelén-Fraile *et al.* (2024) included 116 participants above 65 years gave Yoga with Mediterranean Diet for 12 weeks showed improvements that were not statistically significant but still indicated potential benefits in terms of pain reduction, balance and general physical function.

In a pre- and post-test experimental design involving 30 patients aged 65 to 80 years, a yoga-based exercise therapy program combined with conventional exercises was administered to the experimental group. Timed-Up and Go Test, usual and fast Gait-Speed measured before and after completion of the study. The findings indicated a significant improvement in gait speed scores among older adults who participated in the yoga-based exercise intervention (Karthi *et al.*, 2021). Khuzema *et al.* (2020) conducted an experimental study with 27 patients randomly allocated with three groups yoga group received Home-based Yoga exercise program. The functional mobility was assessed by the Timed 10-m Walk test and Timed Up and Go test. Result shows Yoga could be used as therapeutic intervention to optimize balance and mobility. Groessl *et al.* (2018) recruited 45 participants age between 60- 89 gave silver age yoga for 10 weeks emphasized role of yoga in preventing mobility decline particularly in sedentary individuals pointing to its value in maintaining functional independence. Ni *et al.* (2016) recruited 37 participants age ranged from 60- 90 years in a randomized controlled trial. Significant improvements in gait were reported in study by Ni *et al.* (2016) which used Vinyasa Yoga as intervention for 12 weeks. In a study by Cheung *et al.* (2016) 84 participants randomized age between 60-90 years. Participants received hatha yoga as intervention for 8 weeks. Yoga was better in improving OA symptoms perception, gait, anxiety, and fear

of falling. Variability exists in study design, sample size and outcome measures. The forms of yoga utilized included Vinyasa Yoga, Silver Age Yoga and integrative approaches combining yoga with physiotherapy or dietary modifications. The collective evidence suggests that yoga is a promising low-impact strategy for managing age-related gait decline. Its adaptability for different fitness levels and incorporation into holistic care plans make it especially suitable for older adults.

Table 1: Characteristics of the Included Studies

S. No.	Author (Year)	Study Design	Sample Size/Age group/Intervention on time	Yoga Intervention	Result	Highlights
1	Baek <i>et al.</i> (2025)	Randomized Controlled Trial	46/ mean age 68.7/ 4 nights and 5 days	Mindfulness meditation, focusing on breathing and bodily sensations	Gait ($p < 0.001$)	Significant improvement in all variables of walking ability after intervention.
2	Carcelén-Fraile <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Randomized Controlled Trial	116/>65 yrs/ 12 weeks	Yoga with Mediterranean Diet	Gait Tinetti ($p=0.000$)	Improve the health and functional capacities.
3	Kartha <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Pre and Post-test experimental design	30/65-80 yrs/ 4 weeks	Yoga based exercise therapy program with conventional exercises	Gait ($p < 0.05$)	Significant result in Balance, Mobility and Gait speed scores for the older adults
4	Khuzema <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Experimental study	27/60-85 yrs/8 weeks	Yoga Asana	Gait ($p = 0.001$)	Yoga could be used as therapeutic intervention to optimize balance and mobility.
5	Groessler <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Randomized Controlled Trial	45/60-89 yrs/10 weeks	Silver Age Yoga	Gait ($p = 0.40$)	Prevent mobility limitations among sedentary older adults.
6	Ni <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Randomized Controlled Trial	37/60-90 yrs/ 12 weeks	Vinyasa Yoga	U Walk ($p=0.011$) M Walk ($p=0.008$)	Significantly improve 26 physical performance in older persons with Parkinson Disease.
7	Cheung <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Randomized Controlled Trial	84/60-92 yrs/8 weeks	Hatha Yoga	Gait ($p = 0.006$)	Yoga was better in improving OA symptoms perception, gait, anxiety, and fear of falling.

Conclusion

The findings of this review suggest that yoga interventions have a positive influence on gait performance in older adults. The overall study supports yoga as a safe, low-impact intervention for enhancing gait-related function. Further high-quality, large-scale randomized controlled trials with standardized outcome measures are needed to strengthen the evidence base and guide clinical practice.

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